

National
COVID
Cohort
Collaborative

N3C Query Report: Death (Autopsy)

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Abstract

The overall goal of this query is to quantify deaths (due to any cause) in COVID-19 positive individuals. Here, we look at deaths across subpopulations defined by age, sex, race, hospitalization, and discharge disposition. We repeat all analyses for two definitions of COVID-19 infection (lab-based or diagnosis-based), as well as for either the overall N3C cohort or for a subset composed of only the RECOVER Autopsy sites. Finally, we provide evidence of the trajectory and time course of death after COVID-19 infection. Principally, we find that the majority of deaths occur soon after COVID-19 infection (within 30 days). As a result, this work suggests that mortality more than 90 days after COVID-19 infection is not worse in patients with PASC.

Methods

Inclusion criteria

(see RESULTS for CONSORT diagram)

- **Study period:** 3/1/2020 - 2/28/2022
- **Age:** Any age
- **COVID-19 positive:** via a qualifying index event between 3/1/2020 – 12/31/2021
 - Definition 1. Positive SARS-CoV-2 PCR test (no antibody tests)
 - Definition 2. Diagnosis of COVID-19 via 1 inpatient or 2 outpatient instances of ICD-10 code U07.1
- **Full Cohort:** All patients in the N3C enclave
- **Autopsy Cohort:** All patients that are also from RECOVER Autopsy sites

Data were from release version 72 of the N3C data enclave, released on April 2, 2022. Site-level quality filters were applied prior to analysis in order to remove 13 of the 72 data partners with significant and systematic missingness according to the following criteria: sites (1) should not shift dates by more than 30 days, (2) should have serum creatinine and lymphocyte count results for at least 25% of hospitalizations, and (3) should not have >10% of their hospitalizations where the COVID-19 index date is more than 200 days after the visit start date. Three of these sites were identified to overlap with the RECOVER Autopsy cohort.

Definitions

Index event

The earliest instance of COVID-19 positivity between 3/1/2020 – 12/31/2021. A patient’s first COVID positivity is defined by either Definition 1 or 2 above (lab-based or diagnosis-based).

Patient hospitalization

Hospitalization is defined as occurring within 14 days +/- of the index event.

Patient death

Death is documented if it occurred between the index event and the end of the study period (2/28/2022). Time to death analyses are included. The date of last follow-up is defined as the last recorded date from condition start date, visit end date, measurement date, or procedure date. If the provided death date is before one of these records, the death date was adjusted to be the date of last follow-up. If after this procedure, the date of death or date of last follow-up was after the end of the study period, the patient was considered to be alive at last follow-up, with a date of last follow-up set as the end of the study period. Similarly, dates were required to be before the submission date for each site.

Diagnosis of PASC

PASC was defined as previously described ¹, trained on a cohort of patients who were known to have visited a long-COVID specialty clinic. In order to label a patient as having PASC or not, the patient must meet the following criteria: (1) they must be at least 18 years old, (2) they must have at least 2 days of data in the system, (3) they must have at least one diagnosis and one medication in the pre- or post-index period, and (4) they must have data at least 90 days since the covid index. Approximately 10% of patients with valid COVID index dates do not have sufficient data to determine if they have PASC.

Cell size and patient privacy protection

In order to comply with N3C data use policies, any cell sizes under 20 were suppressed and the surrounding row and column data were adjusted with small gaussian noise in order to obfuscate the suppressed counts.

Results

An accounting of the patients meeting our inclusion criteria for COVID positivity is shown below for each cohort. Of the 12,151,204 patients in the site-filtered cohort described above (from 59 sites), 3,132,942 qualified for the analysis by meeting definition one for COVID positivity, and 849,210 patients qualified by meeting definition two for COVID positivity. 581,234 patients were included in both definitions.

Full Cohort

Definition 1: Test-positive

Table 1. Number of COVID-19 positive patients in the study period, by demographics, hospitalization status, and deceased status

	All COVID	Hospitalized	Not Hospitalized	Deceased	Not Deceased
Age					
Age 0 to 4	86,115 (2.75)	6,412 (1.59)	79,703 (2.92)	69 (0.11)	86,046 (2.8)
Age 5 to 9	104,084 (3.32)	2,308 (0.57)	101,776 (3.73)	35 (0.06)	104,049 (3.39)
Age 10 to 15	173,782 (5.55)	4,639 (1.15)	169,143 (6.2)	57 (0.09)	173,725 (5.66)
Age 16 to 20	222,095 (7.09)	8,903 (2.21)	213,192 (7.81)	153 (0.24)	221,942 (7.23)
Age 21 to 35	779,933 (24.89)	53,157 (13.18)	726,776 (26.63)	1,273 (2.01)	778,660 (25.37)
Age 36 to 45	470,630 (15.02)	42,536 (10.55)	428,094 (15.68)	1,999 (3.16)	468,631 (15.27)
Age 46 to 55	445,919 (14.23)	56,039 (13.89)	389,880 (14.28)	4,653 (7.35)	441,266 (14.38)
Age 56 to 65	403,539 (12.88)	75,052 (18.61)	328,487 (12.03)	10,364 (16.38)	393,175 (12.81)
Age 66+	446,845 (14.26)	154,317 (38.26)	292,528 (10.72)	44,670 (70.6)	402,175 (13.1)
Sex					
Male	144,3876 (46.09)	199,400 (49.43)	1,244,476 (45.59)	35,477 (56.07)	1,408,446 (45.88)
Female	168,2877 (53.72)	203,907 (50.55)	1,478,970 (54.18)	27,833 (43.99)	1,655,045 (53.92)
Other/Unknown	6,189 (0.2)	56 (0.01)	6,133 (0.22)	<20	6,171 (0.2)
Race					
White	1,949,465 (62.22)	223,673 (55.45)	1,725,792 (63.23)	40529 (64.05)	1,908,936 (62.19)
Black	375,508 (11.99)	77,176 (19.13)	298,332 (10.93)	9329 (14.74)	366,179 (11.93)
Hispanic	396,562 (12.66)	63,952 (15.85)	332,610 (12.19)	6583 (10.4)	389,979 (12.7)
Asian	52,200 (1.67)	10,205 (2.53)	41,995 (1.54)	1675 (2.65)	50,525 (1.65)
NHOPI*	3,522 (0.11)	538 (0.13)	2,984 (0.11)	71 (0.11)	3,451 (0.11)
Other	115,005 (3.67)	4,905 (1.22)	110,100 (4.03)	706 (1.12)	114,299 (3.72)
Missing/ Unknown	240,680 (7.68)	22,914 (5.68)	217,766 (7.98)	4380 (6.92)	236,300 (7.7)

*Native Hawaiian or Other Pacific Islander

Table 2. Deaths stratified by hospitalization status, presence of PASC, and timing post-infection/post-discharge

	Discharged alive	Death in hospital	Not hospitalized
Total deaths	19,063	29,756	14,454
within 30 days	7,206	22,400	5,831
after 30 days with PASC	901	553	700
after 30 days without PASC	9,937	4,530	6,332
after 30 days PASC unknown	1,019	2,273	1,591

Definition 2: Diagnosis-positive

Table 1. Number of COVID-19 positive patients in the study period, by demographics, hospitalization status, and deceased status

	All COVID	Hospitalized	Not Hospitalized	Deceased	Not Deceased
Age					
Age 0 to 4	16,291 (1.92)	6,401 (1.69)	9,890 (2.11)	49 (0.09)	16,242 (2.04)
Age 5 to 9	10,353 (1.22)	2,147 (0.57)	8,206 (1.75)	20 (0.04)	10,333 (1.3)
Age 10 to 15	17,490 (2.06)	4,243 (1.12)	13,247 (2.82)	45 (0.08)	17,445 (2.2)
Age 16 to 20	29,339 (3.45)	7,828 (2.06)	21,511 (4.58)	104 (0.19)	29,235 (3.68)
Age 21 to 35	145,753 (17.16)	48,157 (12.68)	97,596 (20.79)	1,105 (2.03)	144,648 (18.2)
Age 36 to 45	114,829 (13.52)	40,750 (10.73)	74,079 (15.78)	1,837 (3.37)	112,992 (14.22)
Age 46 to 55	132,247 (15.57)	54,443 (14.34)	77,804 (16.57)	4,373 (8.02)	127,874 (16.09)
Age 56 to 65	150,216 (17.69)	72,475 (19.08)	77,741 (16.56)	9,467 (17.36)	140,749 (17.71)
Age 66+	232,692 (27.4)	143,324 (37.74)	89,368 (19.04)	37,529 (68.82)	195,163 (24.56)
Sex					
Male	385,810 (45.43)	190,263 (50.1)	195,547 (41.66)	30,988 (56.75)	354,863 (44.65)
Female	463,125 (54.54)	189,447 (49.88)	273,678 (58.3)	23,581 (43.24)	439,545 (55.31)
Other/ Unknown	275 (0.03)	58 (0.02)	217 (0.05)	<20	273 (0.03)
Race					
White	491,862 (57.92)	209,730 (55.23)	282,132 (60.1)	35,247 (64.64)	456,615 (57.46)
Black	132,539 (15.61)	73,336 (19.31)	59,203 (12.61)	8,253 (15.14)	124,286 (15.64)
Hispanic	131,510 (15.49)	59,428 (15.65)	72,082 (15.35)	5,702 (10.46)	125,808 (15.83)
Asian	23,369 (2.75)	10,680 (2.81)	12,689 (2.7)	1,515 (2.78)	21,854 (2.75)
NHOPI*	1,271 (0.15)	581 (0.15)	690 (0.15)	52 (0.1)	1,219 (0.15)
Other	7,029 (0.83)	3,637 (0.96)	3,392 (0.72)	392 (0.72)	6,637 (0.84)
Missing/ Unknown	61,630 (7.26)	22,376 (5.89)	39,254 (8.36)	33,68 (6.18)	58,262 (7.33)

*Native Hawaiian or Other Pacific Islander

Table 2. Deaths stratified by hospitalization status, presence of PASC, and timing post-infection/post-discharge

	Discharged alive	Dead in hospital	Not hospitalized
Total deaths	18,549	29,538	6,442
within 30 days	6,736	21,783	1,939
after 30 days with PASC	953	579	523
after 30 days without PASC	9,808	4,657	3,230
after 30 days PASC unknown	1,052	2,519	750

Autopsy Cohort - Definition 1: Test-positive

Table 1. Number of COVID-19 positive patients in the study period, by demographics, hospitalization status, and deceased status at only the RECOVER Autopsy sites.

	All COVID	Hospitalized	Not Hospitalized	Deceased	Not Deceased
Age					
Age 0 to 4	4,709 (2.65)	314 (1.1)	4,395 (2.94)	0 (0.0)	4,709 (2.71)
Age 5 to 9	6,143 (3.45)	113 (0.39)	6,030 (4.04)	<20	6,151 (3.53)
Age 10 to 15	9,445 (5.31)	197 (0.69)	9,248 (6.19)	<20	9,441 (5.43)
Age 16 to 20	10,765 (6.05)	421 (1.47)	10,344 (6.93)	<20	10,748 (6.18)
Age 21 to 35	43,372 (24.37)	3,677 (12.83)	39,695 (26.58)	43 (1.11)	43,328 (24.9)
Age 36 to 45	26,833 (15.08)	2,929 (10.22)	23,904 (16.01)	94 (2.36)	26,739 (15.37)
Age 46 to 55	24,902 (13.99)	3,665 (12.79)	21,237 (14.22)	256 (6.46)	24,645 (14.16)
Age 56 to 65	24,466 (13.75)	5,278 (18.42)	19,188 (12.85)	561 (14.09)	23,905 (13.74)
Age 66+	27,344 (15.36)	12,065 (42.1)	15,279 (10.23)	3,011 (75.73)	24,329 (13.98)
Sex					
Male	86,020 (48.33)	14,916 (52.05)	71,104 (47.62)	2,378 (59.73)	83,642 (48.07)
Female	91,913 (51.64)	13,743 (47.95)	78,170 (52.35)	1,603 (40.27)	90,310 (51.9)
Other/Unknown	46 (0.03)	0 (0.0)	46 (0.03)	0 (0.0)	46 (0.03)
Race					
White	122,563 (68.86)	16,328 (56.97)	106,235 (71.15)	2,560 (64.26)	120,005 (68.97)
Black	11,550 (6.49)	3,122 (10.89)	8,428 (5.64)	327 (8.19)	11,224 (6.45)
Hispanic	21,572 (12.12)	4,957 (17.3)	16,615 (11.13)	488 (12.23)	21,085 (12.12)
Asian	5,579 (3.13)	1,597 (5.57)	3,982 (2.67)	253 (6.36)	5,326 (3.06)
NHOPI*	203 (0.11)	41 (0.14)	162 (0.11)	<20	203 (0.12)
Other	453 (0.25)	126 (0.44)	327 (0.22)	20 (0.5)	433 (0.25)
Missing/ Unknown	16,059 (9.02)	2,488 (8.68)	13,571 (9.09)	335 (8.41)	15,724 (9.04)

*Native Hawaiian or Other Pacific Islander

Table 2. Deaths stratified by hospitalization status, presence of PASC, and timing post-infection/post-discharge

	Discharged alive	Dead in hospital	Not hospitalized
Total deaths	1,185	2,327	469
within 30 days	420	1,770	110
after 30 days with PASC	84	43	69
after 30 days without PASC	640	368	257
after 30 days PASC unknown	41	146	33

Definition 2: Diagnosis-positive

Table 1. Number of COVID-19 positive patients in the study period, by demographics, hospitalization status, and deceased status at only the RECOVER Autopsy sites.

	All COVID	Hospitalized	Not Hospitalized	Deceased	Not Deceased
Age					
Age 0 to 4	1,469 (1.39)	440 (1.4)	1,029 (1.38)	<20	1,471 (1.45)
Age 5 to 9	1,162 (1.1)	122 (0.39)	1,040 (1.4)	<20	1,160 (1.14)
Age 10 to 15	2,210 (2.09)	209 (0.67)	2,001 (2.69)	<20	2,205 (2.18)
Age 16 to 20	3,713 (3.51)	456 (1.45)	3,257 (4.38)	<20	3,704 (3.66)
Age 21 to 35	19,355 (18.3)	3,884 (12.39)	15,471 (20.79)	47 (1.09)	19,308 (19.03)
Age 36 to 45	14,729 (13.93)	3,181 (10.15)	11,548 (15.52)	93 (2.19)	14,635 (14.42)
Age 46 to 55	16,234 (15.35)	4,074 (13.0)	12,160 (16.34)	277 (6.44)	15,957 (15.73)
Age 56 to 65	19,305 (18.25)	5,879 (18.76)	13,426 (18.04)	612 (14.24)	18,693 (18.42)
Age 66+	27,587 (26.08)	13,100 (41.79)	14,487 (19.47)	3,262 (75.83)	24,328 (23.98)
Sex					
Male	49,987 (47.26)	16,448 (52.47)	33,539 (45.07)	2,529 (58.84)	47,458 (46.77)
Female	55,756 (52.72)	14,897 (47.53)	40,859 (54.9)	1,769 (41.16)	53,987 (53.21)
Other/Unknown	21 (0.02)	0 (0.0)	21 (0.03)	0 (0.0)	21 (0.02)
Race					
White	72,171 (68.24)	18,268 (58.28)	53,903 (72.43)	2,826 (65.7)	69,347 (68.35)
Black	8,072 (7.63)	3,337 (10.65)	4,735 (6.36)	342 (7.96)	7,730 (7.62)
Hispanic	12,949 (12.24)	5,165 (16.48)	7,784 (10.46)	506 (11.77)	12,443 (12.26)
Asian	3,941 (3.73)	1,714 (5.47)	2,227 (2.99)	263 (6.1)	3,679 (3.63)
NHOPI*	125 (0.12)	45 (0.14)	80 (0.11)	<20	123 (0.12)
Other	306 (0.29)	141 (0.45)	165 (0.22)	22 (0.49)	285 (0.28)
Missing/ Unknown	8,200 (7.75)	2,675 (8.53)	5,525 (7.42)	342 (7.93)	7,859 (7.75)

*Native Hawaiian or Other Pacific Islander

Table 2. Deaths stratified by hospitalization status, presence of PASC, and timing post-infection/post-discharge at only the RECOVER Autopsy sites.

	Discharged alive	Dead in hospital	Not hospitalized
Total deaths	1,343	2,468	487
within 30 days	461	1,831	72
after 30 days with PASC	103	47	69
after 30 days without PASC	735	416	326
after 30 days PASC unknown	44	174	20

Survival Trajectories

To illustrate the trajectory of post-infection mortality, a series of Kaplan-Meier curves was created for all patients meeting the above criteria for inclusion through either of the COVID positive definitions. Figure 1 shows survival from index date (stratified by hospitalization), Figure 2 shows survival from date of discharge (stratified by hospitalization), and Figure 3 shows survival from date of discharge (stratified by PASC).

Figure 1. Time to death for hospitalized and non-hospitalized patients from COVID index date.

Figure 2. Time to death for hospitalized patients from discharge and non-hospitalized patients from index

Figure 3. Time to death in patients with a PASC or no-PASC diagnosis. This plot includes patients who were never hospitalized (from index date) as well as patients hospitalized and discharged alive (from the discharge date of their hospitalization). This plot does not include patients for which insufficient utilization was available to confidently diagnose the presence or absence of PASC.

Discussion

Not surprisingly, deaths and hospitalizations are concentrated among older, male, non-white populations. Deaths were also most frequent within 30 days of index infection, especially for hospitalized individuals. A more severe infection, resulting in hospitalization, results in worse survival, even once the patient is discharged from the hospital. In fact, across all cohorts, more deaths occurred in each time period for discharged patients than non-hospitalized patients, with the second most deaths occurring more than 30 days post discharge.

Interestingly, PASC shows no difference for time-to-death from index or discharge in this univariate analysis. In a follow-up analysis that controlled for hospitalization, age, gender, and race, PASC showed a statistically significant but very mild protective effect (OR 0.95). Given the fact that the most deadly period of COVID-19 infection occurs in the weeks following initial infection, and also given that our computable phenotype for PASC requires utilization 90 days after the index infection, by definition, we are excluding the population of people who suffer greatest mortality. Future work may need to address the intermediate time period (28-90 days post-infection) for a more nuanced look at the difference between prolonged acute disease and post-acute disease leading to mortality.

Limitations

One important consideration is that the death data within N3C varies in how well each site and CDM capture post-discharge death and we therefore may be missing counts. Some sites additionally obtain state death registry data or death data from other sources and merge it with in-hospital death before submitting it to N3C, but many do not. While we are making increasing use of death data via PPRL, only a minority of sites are utilizing this functionality at present.

The present study utilizes our pre-existing ML models for computable phenotyping of PASC, however, our models are being continuously updated as we receive more data from sites with U09.9 codes, improve our methods, and have greater opportunity for clinical validation.

References

- 1 Pfaff ER, Girvin AT, Bennett TD, Bhatia A, Brooks IM, Deer RR, *et al.* Who has long-COVID? A big data approach n.d. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.10.18.21265168>.